

Table S4

Content Clusters According to the Variables of Interest in this Systematic Review

References	Independent Variable: Parental Involvement										Dependent Variable: Self-efficacy					Participants						
	Parenting Style		Parental Motivational Actions				Parental Volitional Actions				Academic			Emotional	Social	Students			Parent			
	AUT	CON	SU	AE	AF	MO	PL	EI	TS	CI	HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Affuso et al. (2017)						MO					HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Affuso et al. (2023)						MO					HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Andretta et al. (2017)					AF						HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM		Emotional	ES	MS	HS	M	F
Ben-Tov & Romi (2019)			SU						TS		HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM		Social	ES	MS	HS	M	F
Cross et al. (2019)				AE							HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Dong et al. (2020)						MO			TS	CI	HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Grijalva-Quiñonez et al. (2020)	CON										HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Huang et al. (2021)							PL				HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Kristensen et al. (2023)			SU								HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Liu et al. (2019)			SU								HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Lv et al. (2018)				AE			PL				HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM		Emotional	ES	MS	HS	M	F
Rodríguez et al. (2017)				AE						CI	HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Shi et al. (2024)	CON				AF						HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Sun et al. (2020)					AF						HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Thomas et al. (2019)						MO					HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM			ES	MS	HS	M	F
Xu et al. (2017)		CON									HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM		Emotional	ES	MS	HS	M	F
Yap & Baharudin (2016)			SU								HB	CGM	MM	CNM	BM		Emotional	ES	MS	HS	M	F

Note. **Independent variable:** light orange for information provided by children and dark orange for information provided by parents. Parenting styles: AUT = Autonomy support; CON = Control. Parental motivational actions: SU = Parental support; AE = Aspirations and expectations; AF = Affect. Parental volitional actions: MO = Parental monitoring; PL = Promotion of learning at home; SC = Home-school communication and interest; TS = Task support; CI = Communication and interest in children. **Dependent variable:** Academic self-efficacy: HB = Ability to achieve academic success; CGM = Cognitive management; MM = Motivational management; CNM = Context management; BM = Behavioral management. **Sample:** ES = Elementary school; MS = Middle school; HS = High school; M = Mothers; F = Fathers.